

GRAMMAR AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. The article deals with grammar and its importance in language learning. It firstly gives some information about the meaning of the term grammar. Grammar is explained as a main tool in studying a foreign language in the article. The article highlights that grammar is used to cover all rules such as the rules included in morphology and syntax in the language. Studying a foreign language one needs to master its rules of grammar as well. Having given the information about the history of grammar exactly the first books describing grammar in the history, the article passes its way to the modern period of grammar.

The article touches upon the main points of teaching grammar in a language. Grammar is meant to be one of the main branches in teaching or learning a foreign language in the article. The opinions of linguists about grammar have been described in the article as well.

Key words: *language, learning, grammar, importance, notion, meaning*

Introduction

The word grammar means “art of writing” in Greek. This term explains the meaning of grammar more clearly.

Grammar in any language:

- It involves the systematic study and description of the language;

- It includes a set of rules and examples regarding the syntax and word structures (morphology) of the language;
- The grammar of the English language includes basic axioms such as verb tenses, articles, adjectives (their correct order), how to form questions, how to distinguish words ending in -ing, etc.

D. Crystal describes grammar as following:

- Language cannot function without grammar. We can put it simply: people need grammar to communicate effectively [Crystal D. 2001, p. 34].
- Speakers and listeners, authors and their audiences, must use the same grammatical language to understand each other. In other words, a language without grammar is like a pile of bricks without mortar (to hold them together).
- Grammar is the study of all the possible contrasts of meaning that can be created within sentences. The "rules" of grammar tell us what is what.

Main body

It should be noted that grammar emerged as a product of human thought at a later stage of language development. People created grammar in order to better understand and master the language, to get to the essence of the language, and to explain linguistic phenomena to native speakers and speakers of other foreign languages. That is, language is communication first. Grammar is creation second. Language is not regulated by grammatical laws. Grammatical laws serve to explain the essence of the language, its possibilities of development and use, and its characteristics. Grammar does not create language, it explains it. Grammar should be gradually improved and directs us to understand, analyze, and explain the inexplicables of language [Mahmudov M. 2024, p. 11].

As F.Y. Veysalli noted in his famous book "Introduction to Germanic Linguistics", traditional grammar as a scientific field is a history of multifaceted and diverse knowledge, and in the deep stages of this history there are still unopened doors and contradictory issues [Veysalli F. Y. 2003, p.16]. Just as everything changes in our rapidly changing world, the science of linguistics, especially the field

of grammar, has changed significantly from its inception to the present, different trends, new tendencies, and different approaches to topics have emerged. In order to study, investigate, and analyze grammar as a scientific field in more detail and accurately, it is necessary to look at the path it has taken from the moment its foundation was laid to its current state.

Before analyzing the historical development or structure of any phenomenon or concept, it is necessary to first look at what that phenomenon is and what it represents. So, first of all, let's pay attention to what grammar is and what different approaches to grammar are. Although in ancient Greece and ancient Rome the terms *grammatikē* and grammar were understood as a field that encompassed the science of linguistics as a whole, in the early Middle Ages grammar began to be recorded as the study of the Latin language. In England, this idea continued until the end of the 16th century, and Latin grammar was the only grammar taught in schools. Until this period, English grammar was not thought about [Veysalli F. Y. 2003, p.17].

The first book on English grammar was a book called “Bref Grammar for English” written by William Bullock in 1585. But the most influential and most widely read book was “Short Introduction to English Grammar” by R. Lawes, published in 1762. This book marked the beginning of the era of prescriptive, or normative, grammar. According to the scholar who favored prescriptive grammar, grammar is the science of the correct use of language, and its purpose is not to study its actual use at a particular time, but to study which use is more correct.

The history of linguistics is divided into different stages in terms of time, in which the object of linguistics was different topics. In the early periods, in the European school of linguistics, more precisely in Ancient Greece, language was perceived as a gift from the gods (Plato), or as a consumption created by a group of spirits (Aristotle). During this period, the focus was not on the mechanisms or structure of language, but simply on the phenomenon of language. In addition, the ancient Greeks and Romans conducted various studies on the nature of words and

introduced into linguistics broad lexical categories such as noun, verb, adjective, etc., which are still used today.

Talking about ancient grammar, it is impossible not to mention the services of India in this field. The Indian scholar Panini, who lived in the 4th century BC, provided information about the grammar of times before his time and explained the phonetic structure of the Sanskrit language in more depth. The discovery of Sanskrit, thanks to Panini's great work, not only created conditions for studying the structure of a new language, but also helped to explore the rich grammatical tradition of India [Veysalli F. Y. 2003, p.18].

Between the 5th and 10th centuries, linguistics was one of the slowest-moving scientific institutions to regain its former status. During these centuries, the phenomenon of language was dismissed as a science whose study was not essential, and it was viewed more as a religious discipline. In the 15th century, Stephen Scrope and Anthony Woodville called learning, especially language learning, an internal development, and spoke of achieving it only through the study and study of these sciences. Thus, this decline was put to an end with the Renaissance, and many new directions emerged in linguistics from the 18th century onwards. Some scholars, such as Swift, tried to stabilize a particular language by reducing changes in order to prevent radical new trends in the language. As part of this stabilization, the creation of a standard lexicon and writing form was also a major task. However, the main goal of language stabilization in the 18th century was the creation of a standard scientific grammar in the language. Swift noted that a grammar that is not completely perfect is better than a grammar that is variable. Taking all that has been said, we can say that throughout history, all scholars or linguists have known what grammar is to a greater or lesser extent and have put forward their own hypotheses. But it seemed a little difficult to give a precise definition of the nature of grammar. Until the 20th century, the main goal of linguistics was grammar, and in this way, grammarians had such an influential force that the field of linguistics began to be known as grammar.

Conclusion

English language is known to have taken its way from synthetic to analytic.

There are main aspects in learning a foreign language. One of the key aspects in foreign language learning is meant to be grammar. Grammar is used to form the framework which creates clear and exact communication. Grammar is necessary in writing as well as in speech. Grammar is also used to provide the rules and their structures for making words, phrases, and sentences. It allows people (or language learners) to express their thoughts and ideas neatly.

Currently, new trends in the field of grammar are replacing each other. Grammar, which was once the main nuance in language learning, and the grammar-translation method, which was the dominant method in teaching any language, is observed to be slowly losing their relevance, and a period of transition from linguistic grammar to communicative grammar has begun.

Language learners need grammar to achieve effective writing and speaking skills as well. So, grammar is observed to be essential to develop effective writing and speaking skills. Correct usage of grammar includes coherence, fluency and clarity in writing and speaking. Usage of grammar allows language learners to express themselves clearly, confidently, accurately. Grammar never gives any opportunity for misunderstanding.

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